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Teachers' diary

Session 1 - 06/03/2025

Students attended a session organized by the faculty, where they had the opportunity to speak with former students and professionals in their field about potential career opportunities. They were able to ask questions to a former student of the course, who is currently working as a teacher in a primary school after passing the public examination.

After that, they returned to the classroom, and we conducted a brainstorming session in which several ideas were written on the board in response to the prompt *What do we want to know?* Among the topics discussed we can highlight: the definition of children's literature and its different genres, that characteristics of each genre, and strategies for implementing children's literature effectively in the classroom. After a thoughtful discussion, we reached a consensus on a guiding question that will allow students to explore several topics: *What are the main genres of children's literature and how can each genre be effectively used in foreign language teaching?*

Overall, the students' attitude was very positive, and they actively participated in the session. Although some initially were shy due to their limited linguistic competence in French, they all made the effort to respond when prompted. I did not observe any discomfort among the students, even though it was the first meeting for some of them. Nevertheless, I did not implement a cohesion activity due to limited time and the assumption that all of them already knew each other. However, I plan to include one in future courses to guarantee good group cohesion.

Session 2 – 13/03/2025

Students were asked to form groups of four to discuss three key questions: (1) How would you define children's and young adult literature?, (2) What are their defining characteristics?, and (3) Should children's literature be integrated into the teaching of French as a foreign language and if so, how can it be effectively implemented in the classroom?. We used a cooperative learning strategy called *The revolving sheet*, where each student wrote a response to a question and then passed the sheet to the next group member. Before writing, each student is required to share their intended response with their group to ensure understanding and group responsibility for the answers. Once all questions were answered, definitions were discussed and completed through a productive exchange of ideas.

All students agreed on the importance of using children's literature to learn a foreign language, highlighting its strong motivational potential. As an out-of-class assignment, students were assigned an individual task: to record a video response to a set of reflective questions that addressed their personal reading habits and preferences, their previous knowledge about children's literature in both their native languages and in French, their motivation for choosing this specialization, and their expectations for the subject. This task had a dual purpose: to assess their initial linguistic competence in French in order to provide a more individualized assessment throughout the course, and to assist in the creation of the cooperative teams.

Students were very cooperative with each other. Although some initially chose to form groups with their friends, creating an imbalance between groups, with some of them having 2 or 3 members and others 5 or 6, many did not hesitate when asked to join different peers. Some were reluctant at first but gained confidence after answering the first question together. I still noticed a bit of hesitation

when expressing their opinions, possible due to a lack of confidence in their linguistic abilities. During the activity I noticed that some students were more willing to collaborate and offer help than others, although, overall, they supported each other in a respectful way. This seemed to me to be more of a matter of shyness than unwillingness to help.

Session 3 – 20/03/2025

Before the session the teacher formed the teams through a combination of the observations made on the first session, regarding students' willingness to collaborate and help others during the cooperative activity, and their linguistic competence assessed through the initial video task.

After the distribution, students were asked to complete a form indicating their role in the team (coordinator, secretary, intendant, or aide), along with their personal and shared learning objectives. Afterward, each team was assigned one of the following genres, which were selected from the course syllabus: oral traditional literature (including songs and tales), poetry, picturebooks, theater and comics, and relevant bibliography (including books, scholarly articles and audiovisual materials) was made available via the course's digital platform. The selection was made randomly, as one of the members had to draw a card from a group of cards with different genres written on them.

Once the teams were formed, the next step was to define the final product, as it is the main objective of the PBL methodology. The product was required to have social relevance, either as a physical or digital object or a service, and to meaningfully incorporate ICT tools, allowing students to produce a meaningful, sharable outcome. As it was the first time engaging in this type of project for some students, some were unsure at first. A few suggested creating a blog to document and showcase their work, since they have used this format before. While the idea was considered valuable and was ultimately incorporated into the course, it was clarified that the blog would serve as a platform but cannot be considered a product on its own. Therefore, taking advantage of a newly established radio space at the faculty, we proposed students to develop a radio program as their final product. In this program, each team will present their research on their assigned literary genre, recommend representative books within that genre, and offer strategies for teachers to incorporate the genre into their teaching practices. The radio program will be recorded and published on a digital platform accessible to the community.

For the remainder of the session, students, using the provided bibliography as well as other sources, had to prepare a presentation to share the main findings of their research with their peers. They have to focus their presentations on several key aspects: the definition and main characteristics of the assigned genre, its origins and evolution (including major trends and transformations), notable examples (either originally in French or translated), the educational benefits of the genre in learning a foreign language, and pedagogical objectives. In addition, students will have to include a series of final questions that would be used to design a follow-up questionnaire to assess understanding of the topic, as well as present a practical activity showing an innovative way to incorporate this genre into practice.

Students accepted the distribution of roles done by the teacher without any disagreement and they distributed the roles among themselves with no incidences. They all began to work without any issues, although one team had only one member present, as the others were either sick or participating in a sports competition. This student showed some annoyance at first, especially after receiving a call from a teammate who confirmed they would not be attending, and felt frustrated by the workload. I advised them to divide the task into sections so that their peers could work from

home. If this situation persists in the future, I plan to dissolve the team and either redistribute the members into other teams or create new ones. The other teams showed a very positive attitude, although they struggled a bit to communicate in French with one another.

Session 4 – 27/03/2025

Students shared their presentations with the class. All of them were highly engaged and attentive, taking notes during the presentations, asking questions and actively participating in the planned activities. They acted as if their peers were teachers. While some of them were initially hesitant to speak without a script, and even asked to present in Spanish due to a lack of confidence in their abilities in French, they all made a genuine effort. Those who struggled more clearly needed additional practice beforehand. I was positively surprised by some students who had previously shown difficulty in early sessions, yet managed to present their ideas clearly and effectively.

After the presentations, the next project, the oral traditional literature project, was introduced. For this task, each team was assigned two regions of France, and they had to find a traditional children's song typical of each region. They had to complete a worksheet in which they included regional information (name, localization, major cities, regional languages and main cultural elements), and song details (title, lyrics, language and translation, if sung in a regional language, history of the song and justification for selecting it).

Session 5 – 03/04/2025

Students recorded themselves in the radio space, and simultaneously, in the regular class, they created a collaborative map of France to visually represent the country's cultural diversity. The audio recordings were uploaded in the blog, and each entry was converted into QR codes, which were added to the corresponding regions on the map. The map was displayed at the entrance of the faculty, allowing the community to discover traditional French children's songs.

This activity was very fulfilling for the class and contributed to strong group cohesion. I observed that all the teams worked harmoniously, proposing ideas to add to the map, and they even offered help to other teams what were a little bit behind. During the radio recording, those with better pronunciation supported their peers in pronouncing the lyrics correctly, and some teams even joined in singing each other's songs. I found that this project helped them connect, not only through the designed work but also through the conversations they had during the creative process. Overall, it was a very fulfilling experience for them as a group and for me as a teacher.

After putting up the map on the faculty walls, I introduced the next project, which focuses on comics. To do so, each team was tasked with creating two original comics that incorporated various FLE topics such as vocabulary, idiomatic expressions, or grammar structures. Comics were created using free online applications like *Makebeliefscomix*, although students were encouraged to explore and share other platforms.

Session 6 – 10/04/2025

At the beginning of the lesson, students presented their works in class, discussing their chosen themes, the characters they developed, and the creative process. Students were asked to improvise

as they had not been informed in advance that they would be asked to do so. Some of them showed signs of anxiety or excessive reliance on team members with greater linguistic competence. To address this, questions were directed to other team members to encourage equal participation.

After this activity, we focused in class on exploring a selection of picturebooks and on the technique of rewriting, along with the different types of stories that could be created. Students were tasked with rewriting the ending of *Red Riding Hood*, modernizing a traditional classic story by introducing values such as feminism or environmentalism, and creating a new story based on a photograph, among other tasks. All creations were shared with the class, and a different student was chosen each time to tell the story to avoid having the same individuals speak every time. I noticed that some teams took this activity too seriously and ended up writing very long stories. Although it was encouraged, it limited the number of activities we could do in class, leaving some students feeling overwhelmed. For next year, it might be helpful to establish a word limit or maybe assign different tasks to each team for later comparison.

Since we were talking about rewriting, the students also viewed examples that extended beyond the written page, such as cartoons or advertisements, which led to the introduction of the next project: the creation of a booktube. For this task, students are required to creatively narrate the plot of a book using ICT tools. Each team will choose a picturebook in French and create a *booktrailer* designed to promote the work without revealing the ending. Creativity and originality are highly encouraged.

Session 7 – 24/04/2025

In class, we watched all the booktrailers, and students were asked to reflect on the creative process. Some shared that, at first, it was challenging, since they had to carefully choose the scenarios and decide which parts of the story they wanted to include. However, they also said it was a very enriching experience that allowed them to express themselves freely in a way they have not experienced before. After each booktrailer, students from the other teams applauded and congratulated their peers, which made them feel proud and appreciated, knowing that their efforts were being recognized by their classmates.

After that, the theater project was introduced. Each team selected a picturebook and began writing the script for a play to be performed in class. They were also responsible for designing the set and costumes, preferably using recycled materials. Additionally, students were required to engage interactively with the audience during the performance, simulating a real scenario as if performing for a group of children. Some students had difficulty choosing the right picturebook, with several teams changing their selection multiple times due to uncertainty about the perspective they wanted to take. I was present throughout the process, sharing my experience, helping them create the outline of the script, and offering creative suggestions. It is worth noting that some students initially attempted to create very literal interpretations of the books, which led to several challenges. I had to remind them that it was an adaptation, and that it should be adapted to fit the classroom context, especially since it was encouraged to use recycled materials and make the most of available resources. Regarding team and classroom dynamics, I observed a strong sense of cohesion both within each team and across the entire class. Students shared their ideas with other teams and offered support when they were stuck, fostering a very collaborative atmosphere. Even students who never worked together were able to forge meaningful connections.

Session 8 – 08/05/2025

Students performed their plays in front of their classmates, and it proved to be a very enriching experience in which everyone participated. Some teams focused their audience interactions on answering questions or repeating phrases, while others invited classmates on stage to take part in the play. Overall, the atmosphere was very positive, and not a single student refused to participate. One team had to improvise since one of its members was unable to attend, and they handled the situation successfully by interacting with a recording of the absent student projected on the screen. It is worth noting that most students chose not to memorize the entire script but instead learned some key phrases and improvised parts of the dialogue, which resulted in natural, engaging performances. They made effective use of the performance space, and all props and costumes were created using recycled materials. All performances were recorded for later evaluation.

Students were tasked with writing the script for the radio program they will record next week. To do so, they had to review their previous presentations and bibliography, incorporate the teacher's feedback, and apply all the knowledge they have gained throughout the course. Specific guidelines were provided to ensure that all the programs followed a consistent structure. All teams quickly got to work to start writing the script and sought help when needed, especially with aspects related to pronunciation. I recommended that they record themselves beforehand to practice in order to improve their intonation and fluency before the final recording.

Session 9 – 15/05/2025

Throughout this session, teams took turns to go to the radio station and record their programs. I went with them to provide support and ensure that everything was working properly, as the recordings were lengthy and it would have been quite frustrating to have to redo them several times. While one team was recording, the rest of the teams were engaged in another activity: the poetry project. Students had to select an emotion and were asked to imagine its characteristics such as its color, smell, shape, sound, behavior, or where it might live. Using public domain images databases, they searched for visuals that evoked that emotion and created a virtual collage as a source of inspiration. Based on this, they wrote an original poem and embedded it within the collage. In addition, they were required to create a calligram, an acrostic and a tautogram related to their chosen emotion and poem. During the recording, all students were highly participative and supported one another, particularly with pronunciation. I advised them to keep talking even if they made a mistake, as the recordings were going to be edited later. I also went downstairs several times to check on the students working on the poetry activity, and all of them reported that it was going well and that no further assistance was required.

Students were required to edit the radio programs using Audacity (adding music and sound effects, deleting unnecessary fragments or mistakes, and adjusting voice volume for consistency). Once completed, the recordings were uploaded to the Moodle platform, where students would self-assess their performance using a shared rubric and also evaluate their peers' recordings. Since only a few had used Audacity before, I created a tutorial to guide them through the process, which they greatly appreciated. I was pleasantly surprised to see that they were no longer shy about sharing their recordings with classmates, something that would have been impossible at the beginning of the course. This shift reflected real progress not only in their confidence, but also in their perception of teaching, as a process of growth, where making mistakes is part of learning and not something to be judged for.

Session 10 – 22/05/2025

We concluded the course by working with a scientific article on the use of literary texts on the French as a foreign language classroom. The objective was to engage students in reading academic literature and understanding its implications for teaching practice. We used the expert group technique: each team was assigned a different section of the text and had to read them to their peers out loud, identify the key points, summarize it, find interesting or field-specific words and expressions typical of academic writing, and propose a hypothesis to continue the text. Afterward, it was planned that one member of each team joined others with the same number to form new groups. Together, they will have to complete a table including the main ideas, the contribution of the article to the teaching of French as a foreign language, and potential questions for discussion.

Students worked very well in their respective team, however, many expressed that the task was challenging since they were not accustomed to engaging with academic texts in French at such deep level. As a result, we did not have enough time to complete the final discussion in the expert groups. Instead, I shared a group table, and each original team had to complete it, sharing their ideas with the class and the end.

As final remarks, I can confidently say that this has been one of the most rewarding experiences I have had teaching this course. I observed significant progress in student autonomy, teamwork, and overall group cohesion. Their confidence also grew, both in their language skills and their willingness to share their work and ideas without fear of making mistakes. Students expressed that they found the activities highly useful, not only in terms of learning the course's content or developing their language abilities, but also in learning how to implement similar activities in their own future classrooms, using PBL methodology. For the first time, I saw students eager to stay after class, even after five hours of work, which greatly shows their level of engagement and motivation. I plan to implement this methodology in the coming years, as well as adapt it to other subjects.

Questionnaires

Student 1

Oral literature

How did the activity go?

Very well

Have you encountered any difficulties?

No

If so, what solutions have you adopted as a team?

On a scale from 1 to 5, how would you rate this activity?

5 out of 5

What have you learned from this activity?

I got to know the different regions of France and its traditional songs

How would you rate teamwork?

Excellent

What were the positive aspects of your teamwork?

Coordination and organization

What aspects of teamwork do you think need improving?

For this project, nothing

Comics

How did the activity go?

Very well

Have you encountered any difficulties?

Yes

If so, what solutions have you adopted as a team?

We have trouble choosing the adequate website, since the only ones that offered a wide variety of tools were payable.

On a scale from 1 to 5, how would you rate this activity?

5 out of 5

What have you learned from this activity?

We learned who to use comics as a tool for teaching a foreign language

How would you rate teamwork?

Excellent

What were the positive aspects of your teamwork?

Collaboration and communication between members.

What aspects of teamwork do you think need improving?

Nothing

Picturebooks

How did the activity go?

Very well

Have you encountered any difficulties?

Yes

If so, what solutions have you adopted as a team?

We had a few problems with the character costumes. We had to make the most of our creativity.

On a scale from 1 to 5, how would you rate this activity?

4 out of 5

What have you learned from this activity?

I learned how to create a booktrailer. What's more, I've seen how important these activities are for developing a taste for reading and encouraging students to read more.

How would you rate teamwork?

Excellent

What were the positive aspects of your teamwork?

The positive points of our team are its coordination, organization and good atmosphere.

What aspects of teamwork do you think need improving?

To put it gently, we need to improve our concentration when we're working, because we're often distracted.

Theater

How did the activity go?

Very well

Have you encountered any difficulties?

Yes

If so, what solutions have you adopted as a team?

The only difficulty we encountered was how to shorten the dialogue of the picturebook so that we could memorize it without losing the context of the story

On a scale from 1 to 5, how would you rate this activity?

5 out of 5

What have you learned from this activity?

This activity has allowed me to better understand the importance of theater in a primary school classroom. Theater allows students to work on oral expression, acting, vocalization and body language

How would you rate teamwork?

Excellent

What were the positive aspects of your teamwork?

Liberty to speak our minds and support our ideas

What aspects of teamwork do you think need improving?

Nothing

Poetry

How did the activity go?

Very well

Have you encountered any difficulties?

Yes

If so, what solutions have you adopted as a team?

The difficulty we encountered in this activity was finding rhyming words for creating the poem. We had to use the Internet to find words with the same ending sounds.

On a scale from 1 to 5, how would you rate this activity?

5 out of 5

What have you learned from this activity?

Thanks to this activity, I learned how easy, fun, and rewarding it is to work with poetry. With primary school children, there are many resources and different ways to work with poetry, adapting it to the students' characteristics and interests.

How would you rate teamwork?

Excellent

What were the positive aspects of your teamwork?

Coordination, organization and good atmosphere.

What aspects of teamwork do you think need improving?

Nothing

Presentation and radio

How did the activity go?

Very well

Have you encountered any difficulties?

No

If so, what solutions have you adopted as a team?

On a scale from 1 to 5, how would you rate this activity?

5 out of 5

What have you learned from this activity?

This activity allowed me to learn about different creative activities to do in class with my future students related to comics, poetry, and other genres. I enjoyed the creation of the podcast, I found it very interesting and fun.

How would you rate teamwork?

Excellent

What were the positive aspects of your teamwork?

We coordinated very well, and it was very easy for us to work and stay organized.

What aspects of teamwork do you think need improving?

Nothing

Student 2

Oral literature

How did the activity go?

Very well

Have you encountered any difficulties?

No

If so, what solutions have you adopted as a team?

On a scale from 1 to 5, how would you rate this activity?

5 out of 5

What have you learned from this activity?

I learned a lot about the different regions of France and the popular children's songs of each region.

How would you rate teamwork?

Excellent

What were the positive aspects of your teamwork?

Coordination and confidence in our work

What aspects of teamwork do you think need improving?

Nothing

Comics

How did the activity go?

Very well

Have you encountered any difficulties?

Yes

If so, what solutions have you adopted as a team?

We had a hard time finding a website that let us create comics for free, and that offered a wide variety of creative possibilities.

On a scale from 1 to 5, how would you rate this activity?

5 out of 5

What have you learned from this activity?

I've learned that creating and/or reading comic strips is an excellent pedagogical tool to apply in primary education.

How would you rate teamwork?

Excellent

What were the positive aspects of your teamwork?

We excelled in collaboration, with each member contributing valuable ideas. Constant communication and mutual support enabled us to overcome obstacles and achieve our common goal.

What aspects of teamwork do you think need improving?

We didn't identify any areas for improvement, as we managed to maintain a very positive organization and working atmosphere throughout the process.

*Picturebooks***How did the activity go?**

Very well

Have you encountered any difficulties?

No

If so, what solutions have you adopted as a team?

No, the teamwork was well organized and we easily agreed on the ideas and distribution of scenes. The only difficulty we encountered was characterization, since we wanted them to resemble the characters in the story as closely as possible, and it wasn't always easy to find the right props.

On a scale from 1 to 5, how would you rate this activity?

5 out of 5

What have you learned from this activity?

I learned what a booktrailer is and how to make one. I also learned how to summarize a story in a visually appealing way, and how to work in a team to organize and complete all phases of the project.

How would you rate teamwork?

Excellent

What were the positive aspects of your teamwork?

We organized ourselves well right from the start and distributed the tasks evenly. We all contributed ideas and respected each other's opinions. Moreover, there was a very good working atmosphere, which made the whole process easier and more enjoyable.

What aspects of teamwork do you think need improving?

We should improve our ability to make decisions more quickly and not overthink them. Sometimes we took too long reaching a decision, which caused us to lose time on other parts of the activity.

Theater

How did the activity go?

Very well

Have you encountered any difficulties?

Yes

If so, what solutions have you adopted as a team?

We had difficulty assigning the characters and presenting the story to the rest of the class. Another challenge was choosing the story, as we had many doubts about how to portray it and make the most of it. Additionally, we created a very long dialogue and we didn't know what to cut.

On a scale from 1 to 5, how would you rate this activity?

5 out of 5

What have you learned from this activity?

This activity allowed me to develop my theatrical skills and overcome my stage fright in front of others. I also expanded my knowledge on how to build a story with rich context based on a picturebook, through which we were able to showcase our competences to our classmates.

How would you rate teamwork?

Excellent

What were the positive aspects of your teamwork?

Good communication and cooperation.

What aspects of teamwork do you think need improving?

Better distribution of time and better skills at problem-solving

Poetry

How did the activity go?

Very well

Have you encountered any difficulties?

Yes

If so, what solutions have you adopted as a team?

We had two problems. First, it was difficult to find images without copyright issues for the collage. For that, we used a website with free images. Then, for the poem, it was hard to find rhyming words. But we found a website where you type a word, and it gives you rhyming words. That helped us a lot.

On a scale from 1 to 5, how would you rate this activity?

5 out of 5

What have you learned from this activity?

This activity taught me how to create different types of texts, such as poems, tautograms, calligrams, and acrostics. I also improved my creativity and my ability to find rhymes.

How would you rate teamwork?

Excellent

What were the positive aspects of your teamwork?

I think we worked very well together

What aspects of teamwork do you think need improving?

Nothing

Presentation and radio

How did the activity go?

Very well

Have you encountered any difficulties?

No

If so, what solutions have you adopted as a team?

On a scale from 1 to 5, how would you rate this activity?

4 out of 5

What have you learned from this activity?

I learned a lot about the different literary genres and how to use them in a primary school classroom, especially picture books.

How would you rate teamwork?

Excellent

What were the positive aspects of your teamwork?

We organized ourselves well, we all collaborated to create a clear presentation and suitable activities, and everyone was involved in the project editing the audio. We all contributed ideas, listened to, and valued each other's opinions.

What aspects of teamwork do you think need improving?

Nothing, everything worked properly.

Student 3

Oral literature

How did the activity go?

Very well

Have you encountered any difficulties?

No

If so, what solutions have you adopted as a team?

On a scale from 1 to 5, how would you rate this activity?

5 out of 5

What have you learned from this activity?

France's regions and typical songs as well as their culture, flag, symbol, etc.

How would you rate teamwork?

Excellent

What were the positive aspects of your teamwork?

Good teamwork and interaction between members.

What aspects of teamwork do you think need improving?

Better organization of our time.

Comics

How did the activity go?

Very well

Have you encountered any difficulties?

Yes

If so, what solutions have you adopted as a team?

One of the applications only allowed three images, we had to be creative.

On a scale from 1 to 5, how would you rate this activity?

5 out of 5

What have you learned from this activity?

I learned French expressions and how to use an application for creating comics.

How would you rate teamwork?

Excellent

What were the positive aspects of your teamwork?

Organization.

What aspects of teamwork do you think need improving?

The use of technology.

Picturebooks

How did the activity go?

Very well

Have you encountered any difficulties?

No

If so, what solutions have you adopted as a team?

On a scale from 1 to 5, how would you rate this activity?

5 out of 5

What have you learned from this activity?

How to create a new story from a picturebook.

How would you rate teamwork?

Excellent

What were the positive aspects of your teamwork?

Teamwork in general

What aspects of teamwork do you think need improving?

We have to improve pronunciation in French as a team.

Theater

How did the activity go?

Very well

Have you encountered any difficulties?

No

If so, what solutions have you adopted as a team?

On a scale from 1 to 5, how would you rate this activity?

5 out of 5

What have you learned from this activity?

We learned new concepts about theater in class and we were able to perform in front of our peers.

How would you rate teamwork?

Excellent

What were the positive aspects of your teamwork?

Teamwork in general was great and we complemented each other.

What aspects of teamwork do you think need improving?

Nothing

Poetry

How did the activity go?

Very well

Have you encountered any difficulties?

No

If so, what solutions have you adopted as a team?

On a scale from 1 to 5, how would you rate this activity?

5 out of 5

What have you learned from this activity?

Learn what a tautogram, a calligram, and an acrostic are and learn how to use it in French as a foreign language.

How would you rate teamwork?

Excellent

What were the positive aspects of your teamwork?

We worked very well together.

What aspects of teamwork do you think need improving?

Nothing

Presentation and radio

How did the activity go?

Very well

Have you encountered any difficulties?

No

If so, what solutions have you adopted as a team?

On a scale from 1 to 5, how would you rate this activity?

5 out of 5

What have you learned from this activity?

A lot of information about comics and different genres that I didn't know before.

How would you rate teamwork?

Good

What were the positive aspects of your teamwork?

Good organization.

What aspects of teamwork do you think need improving?

Start the tasks earlier for having more time.

Student 4

Oral literature

How did the activity go?

Very well

Have you encountered any difficulties?

No

If so, what solutions have you adopted as a team?

On a scale from 1 to 5, how would you rate this activity?

5 out of 5

What have you learned from this activity?

This activity introduced me to several regions of France, some of its regional songs and its culture.

How would you rate teamwork?

Excellent

What were the positive aspects of your teamwork?

Coordination and confidence.

What aspects of teamwork do you think need improving?

Nothing

Comics

How did the activity go?

Very well

Have you encountered any difficulties?

Yes

If so, what solutions have you adopted as a team?

The difficulty we encountered was in creating the comic strips, as the available applications allowed us to add interesting images were all pay ware. To solve this problem, our team chose Storyboard, the application that offered the freest resources, and took advantage of it. Once we'd created the comic strip in Storyboard, we pasted everything into Canva so we could organize it better.

On a scale from 1 to 5, how would you rate this activity?

5 out of 5

What have you learned from this activity?

Through this activity, I learned how interesting and enriching it can be to work with children in the field of comics. What's more, I was able to see the wide variety of resources and content that can be worked with comics. As far as observations are concerned, I'd like to say that in general the activity was very interesting and that working with my team was very positive for me. I'd also like to point out that the work presented by the other students was excellent.

How would you rate teamwork?

Excellent

What were the positive aspects of your teamwork?

Among the positive aspects of the teamwork, I'd like to highlight the following: we got on very well when choosing the application to make the comic strip, and it was also very easy to organize ourselves because we understood each other very well when carrying out the activity.

What aspects of teamwork do you think need improving?

As an aspect to improve as a team, I'd point out that at first we were a little hesitant to choose the application, as we wanted to make a very interesting comic strip with great visual richness. In addition, we should improve our use of time, as we may have hesitated several times when starting the activity.

Picturebooks

How did the activity go?

Very well

Have you encountered any difficulties?

Yes

If so, what solutions have you adopted as a team?

We had difficulty recording the videos and inserting the audios. Another difficulty was the choice of story, as we had many doubts about how to create an interesting booktrailer.

On a scale from 1 to 5, how would you rate this activity?

5 out of 5

What have you learned from this activity?

This activity enabled me to learn how to create a booktrailer in an interactive way. In addition, I was able to broaden my knowledge of stories and develop my skills in showing the strengths of reading.

How would you rate teamwork?

Excellent

What were the positive aspects of your teamwork?

As for the positive aspects of teamwork, since some of us have been working together for several years, we have an excellent rapport, both in discussing ideas we have for the activity and in organizing ourselves to meet the activity schedule. By way of concluding remarks, I'd like to say that

as a team we worked very well and, as far as this activity was concerned, although we had our doubts about the choice of story on which to make the trailer, we did a very good job as a team..

What aspects of teamwork do you think need improving?

As for the aspects of our teamwork that need improving, it's worth pointing out that, although we have a very good relationship, there are also things that need improving. For example, I think we need to improve when it comes to deciding more quickly how we want to develop the project, and also when we have doubts whether the ideas we have are good or not.

Theater

How did the activity go?

Very well

Have you encountered any difficulties?

Yes

If so, what solutions have you adopted as a team?

We had difficulty assigning the characters and presenting the story to the rest of the class. Another challenge was choosing the story, as we had many doubts about how to portray it and make the most of it. Additionally, we created a very long dialogue and we didn't know what to cut.

On a scale from 1 to 5, how would you rate this activity?

5 out of 5

What have you learned from this activity?

This activity allowed me to develop my theatrical skills and overcome my stage fright in front of others. I also expanded my knowledge on how to build a story with rich context based on a picturebook, through which we were able to showcase our competences to our classmates.

How would you rate teamwork?

Excellent

What were the positive aspects of your teamwork?

Good communication and cooperation.

What aspects of teamwork do you think need improving?

Better distribution of time and better skills at problem-solving

Poetry

How did the activity go?

Very well

Have you encountered any difficulties?

Yes

If so, what solutions have you adopted as a team?

We had difficulties choosing the emotion, as well as associating it with a smell, a color, a shape, etc. To solve this problem, we decided to suggest several emotions and choose together the one we liked the most.

On a scale from 1 to 5, how would you rate this activity?

5 out of 5

What have you learned from this activity?

This activity allowed me to develop my poetic skills related to the emotion of fear and to discover some of the poetic forms we worked on. Additionally, we were able to work very well as a team and develop very interesting skills related to poetry and the composition of tautograms, acrostics, and calligrams.

How would you rate teamwork?

Excellent

What were the positive aspects of your teamwork?

We worked very well as a team

What aspects of teamwork do you think need improving?

Nothing

Presentation and radio

How did the activity go?

Very well

Have you encountered any difficulties?

No

If so, what solutions have you adopted as a team?

On a scale from 1 to 5, how would you rate this activity?

5 out of 5

What have you learned from this activity?

By doing this activity, I learned a lot about picturebooks and, above all, I practiced my French more. Overall, I found this activity very interesting because it allowed me to actively develop a radio show and, above all, to work on my oral skills in French. Additionally, I want to highlight that, on one hand, individually, it seemed very enriching to me for gaining confidence in speaking French dynamically; on the other hand, as a team, we worked very well together, although I would say we still need to

improve our communicative fluency and pronunciation. It was a very rewarding and enjoyable activity!

How would you rate teamwork?

Excellent

What were the positive aspects of your teamwork?

The positive aspects of teamwork, especially with my colleagues, are as follows: good understanding during the development of activities, interesting ideas, good communication, and efficient and cooperative work.

What aspects of teamwork do you think need improving?

The aspects we can improve as a team are as follows: deciding more quickly on the final idea for the activity without relying on an extensive brainstorming session.

Student 5

Oral literature

How did the activity go?

Very well

Have you encountered any difficulties?

No

If so, what solutions have you adopted as a team?

On a scale from 1 to 5, how would you rate this activity?

5 out of 5

What have you learned from this activity?

I got to know the different regions of France and their characteristics and traditions.

How would you rate teamwork?

Excellent

What were the positive aspects of your teamwork?

We always look for the strengths in others and build on them. We like to work as a team.

What aspects of teamwork do you think need improving?

For the moment, I feel comfortable with the work we're doing

Comics

How did the activity go?

Very well

Have you encountered any difficulties?

No

If so, what solutions have you adopted as a team?

On a scale from 1 to 5, how would you rate this activity?

5 out of 5

What have you learned from this activity?

I didn't know about the applications to create comic strips. I knew about the "Pixton" application, so I'm happy to discover other tools allows us to create comic strips easily.

How would you rate teamwork?

Excellent

What were the positive aspects of your teamwork?

We complement each other very well. We listen to each other for good ideas to implement.

What aspects of teamwork do you think need improving?

Perhaps we should design a step-by-step plan before starting the activity.

Picturebooks

How did the activity go?

Very well

Have you encountered any difficulties?

Yes

If so, what solutions have you adopted as a team?

As we live in different parts of the region, it was a bit difficult to organize the work, as we couldn't meet up in person and we all wanted to appear in the video.

On a scale from 1 to 5, how would you rate this activity?

5 out of 5

What have you learned from this activity?

Thanks to this activity, I discovered a new way of working with a book. The fact that I had to make a video as if it was a film trailer was very interesting for me. Until now, I'd only done things like changing the ending of a story or a character's personality.

How would you rate teamwork?

Excellent

What were the positive aspects of your teamwork?

I think we adapted well to the situation, i.e. the fact that we couldn't get together to record the videos. What's more, I think we were creative.

What aspects of teamwork do you think need improving?

I think we've organized ourselves well, but we could improve communication and distribute roles better.

Theater

How did the activity go?

Very well

Have you encountered any difficulties?

Yes

If so, what solutions have you adopted as a team?

Designing the scene changes was challenging, but I think we managed by turning the lights on and off. Also, I believe our script was too complicated, and we ended up adapting it a bit during the performance.

On a scale from 1 to 5, how would you rate this activity?

5 out of 5

What have you learned from this activity?

I learned a new way of working with a picturebook in the classroom, and I reflected on ways to interact with students through a performance.

How would you rate teamwork?

Excellent

What were the positive aspects of your teamwork?

I am very satisfied with all the aspects of teamwork.

What aspects of teamwork do you think need improving?

Nothing

Poetry

How did the activity go?

Very well

Have you encountered any difficulties?

Yes

If so, what solutions have you adopted as a team?

At first, we didn't know what type of images to use without them being repetitive, and on top of that, they had to be royalty-free so we could use them. As a solution, we searched on several websites like Freepik. Then, it was difficult to find rhyming words to write the poem. Finally, we consulted some examples on a website.

On a scale from 1 to 5, how would you rate this activity?

5 out of 5

What have you learned from this activity?

I learned how to use different techniques to introduce students to poetic creation in a playful way. Also, I didn't know about tautograms before, and I found them very interesting.

How would you rate teamwork?

Excellent

What were the positive aspects of your teamwork?

We worked very well as a team

What aspects of teamwork do you think need improving?

Nothing

Presentation and radio

How did the activity go?

Very well

Have you encountered any difficulties?

No

If so, what solutions have you adopted as a team?

On a scale from 1 to 5, how would you rate this activity?

5 out of 5

What have you learned from this activity?

This activity was an opportunity to learn what a picturebook is, as I used to confuse it with another genre. I also think using the radio was a good experience to learn and improve my pronunciation, as I think that I made a few small pronunciation mistakes and sometimes my tone wasn't very dynamic, but I think it was because of stress. Despite that, I managed to communicate my ideas well and follow the flow of my speech.

How would you rate teamwork?

Excellent

What were the positive aspects of your teamwork?

I think that communication and organization were very good. I am very satisfied with my team.

What aspects of teamwork do you think need improving?

I think we need to improve the way we introduce ourselves and address the audience.

Student 6

Oral literature

How did the activity go?

Very well

Have you encountered any difficulties?

No

If so, what solutions have you adopted as a team?

On a scale from 1 to 5, how would you rate this activity?

5 out of 5

What have you learned from this activity?

We got to know France and its different regions, cultural features and curiosities.

How would you rate teamwork?

Excellent

What were the positive aspects of your teamwork?

Good organization and predisposition.

What aspects of teamwork do you think need improving?

Communication outside the classroom.

Comics

How did the activity go?

Very well

Have you encountered any difficulties?

No

If so, what solutions have you adopted as a team?

On a scale from 1 to 5, how would you rate this activity?

5 out of 5

What have you learned from this activity?

A fun and entertaining way to teach French.

How would you rate teamwork?

Excellent

What were the positive aspects of your teamwork?

Good organization and a work well done.

What aspects of teamwork do you think need improving?

Creativity.

Picturebooks

How did the activity go?

Very well

Have you encountered any difficulties?

No

If so, what solutions have you adopted as a team?

On a scale from 1 to 5, how would you rate this activity?

5 out of 5

What have you learned from this activity?

I learned more about classic children's literature, acquired new vocabulary and also developed my creativity. As a team we have really appreciated this activity.

How would you rate teamwork?

Excellent

What were the positive aspects of your teamwork?

Good organization and availability.

What aspects of teamwork do you think need improving?

Perhaps improve our pronunciation a little, specially fluidity.

Theater

How did the activity go?

Very well

Have you encountered any difficulties?

No

If so, what solutions have you adopted as a team?

On a scale from 1 to 5, how would you rate this activity?

5 out of 5

What have you learned from this activity?

Through this activity, we learned how to convey situations and emotions through theater. It helped us overcome stage fright and discover new ways to work with children in a foreign language.

How would you rate teamwork?

Excellent

What were the positive aspects of your teamwork?

We worked very well together. I am very satisfied with my team.

What aspects of teamwork do you think need improving?

Nothing

Poetry

How did the activity go?

Very well

Have you encountered any difficulties?

No

If so, what solutions have you adopted as a team?

On a scale from 1 to 5, how would you rate this activity?

5 out of 5

What have you learned from this activity?

With this activity, we learned to work more creatively with classic concepts and discovered types of activities to encourage imagination and develop the thinking of both children and adults learning a foreign language.

How would you rate teamwork?

Excellent

What were the positive aspects of your teamwork?

Creativity

What aspects of teamwork do you think need improving?

Nothing

Presentation and radio

How did the activity go?

Very well

Have you encountered any difficulties?

No

If so, what solutions have you adopted as a team?

On a scale from 1 to 5, how would you rate this activity?

5 out of 5

What have you learned from this activity?

I discovered the different types of literature for children and young adults and how to implement them in foreign language classes, as well as the benefits of using the radio.

How would you rate teamwork?

Excellent

What were the positive aspects of your teamwork?

Good coordination and engagement.

What aspects of teamwork do you think need improving?

Lack of creativity.

Student 7

Oral literature

How did the activity go?

Very well

Have you encountered any difficulties?

No

If so, what solutions have you adopted as a team?

On a scale from 1 to 5, how would you rate this activity?

5 out of 5

What have you learned from this activity?

Typical French songs, flags, typical foods, symbols and regions.

How would you rate teamwork?

Excellent

What were the positive aspects of your teamwork?

Teamwork in general.

What aspects of teamwork do you think need improving?

Division of labor: some people had a heavier workload.

Comics

How did the activity go?

Very well

Have you encountered any difficulties?

Yes

If so, what solutions have you adopted as a team?

Certain applications for creating comic vignettes were limited to the number of vignettes that could be created. The solution we adopted for the creation of vignettes in the application was to create different e-mail addresses.

On a scale from 1 to 5, how would you rate this activity?

5 out of 5

What have you learned from this activity?

We learned to create a comic.

How would you rate teamwork?

Excellent

What were the positive aspects of your teamwork?

Cooperative work.

What aspects of teamwork do you think need improving?

In this activity, none, since we've organized ourselves very well.

Picturebooks

How did the activity go?

Very well

Have you encountered any difficulties?

Yes

If so, what solutions have you adopted as a team?

In the division of labor, some people worked harder than others.

On a scale from 1 to 5, how would you rate this activity?

5 out of 5

What have you learned from this activity?

To work in cooperation with team members involved and to use different applications to create a video.

How would you rate teamwork?

Good

What were the positive aspects of your teamwork?

There were no disagreements in the execution of the work, and the main ideas were implemented right from the start.

What aspects of teamwork do you think need improving?

Better distribution of tasks

Theater

How did the activity go?

Very well

Have you encountered any difficulties?

No

If so, what solutions have you adopted as a team?

On a scale from 1 to 5, how would you rate this activity?

5 out of 5

What have you learned from this activity?

In this activity, we worked together to produce a play from a children's story, taking into account its different parts.

How would you rate teamwork?

Excellent

What were the positive aspects of your teamwork?

Creativity and communication.

What aspects of teamwork do you think need improving?

We didn't have any problems or issues within the team while completing the activity. The activity went smoothly with the team.

Poetry

How did the activity go?

Very well

Have you encountered any difficulties?

No

If so, what solutions have you adopted as a team?

On a scale from 1 to 5, how would you rate this activity?

5 out of 5

What have you learned from this activity?

Through the use of different words, we created a poem among the four team members as well as various activities.

How would you rate teamwork?

Excellent

What were the positive aspects of your teamwork?

Creativity.

What aspects of teamwork do you think need improving?

We didn't encounter any difficulties, because all four team members did it in class.

Presentation and radio

How did the activity go?

Very well

Have you encountered any difficulties?

No

If so, what solutions have you adopted as a team?

On a scale from 1 to 5, how would you rate this activity?

5 out of 5

What have you learned from this activity?

This activity allowed me to deepen my knowledge of comics and strengthen my teamwork skills. Together, we collaborated to complete the various assigned steps. Moreover, I like creating podcasts.

How would you rate teamwork?

Excellent

What were the positive aspects of your teamwork?

The fact that we did it together, since the workload was considerable.

What aspects of teamwork do you think need improving?

Better distribution of the workload

Student 8

Oral literature

How did the activity go?

Very well

Have you encountered any difficulties?

No

If so, what solutions have you adopted as a team?

On a scale from 1 to 5, how would you rate this activity?

5 out of 5

What have you learned from this activity?

A very interesting and motivating way to teach language through rhymes and Francophonie.

How would you rate teamwork?

Excellent

What were the positive aspects of your teamwork?

Very good environment and teamwork.

What aspects of teamwork do you think need improving?

A little more organization.

Comics

How did the activity go?

Very well

Have you encountered any difficulties?

No

If so, what solutions have you adopted as a team?

On a scale from 1 to 5, how would you rate this activity?

5 out of 5

What have you learned from this activity?

Websites to create resources for working with comics in a foreign language class.

How would you rate teamwork?

Excellent

What were the positive aspects of your teamwork?

I believe our project was well done and we have worked a lot. I think that I worked better this time.

What aspects of teamwork do you think need improving?

Better organization of time

Picturebooks

How did the activity go?

Well

Have you encountered any difficulties?

No

If so, what solutions have you adopted as a team?

On a scale from 1 to 5, how would you rate this activity?

5 out of 5

What have you learned from this activity?

This work has enabled me to develop my creativity and scripting skills to build a coherent visual narrative.

How would you rate teamwork?

Excellent

What were the positive aspects of your teamwork?

We have all helped a lot with the creation of the script.

What aspects of teamwork do you think need improving?

Availability to set up appointments.

Theater

How did the activity go?

Very well

Have you encountered any difficulties?

No

If so, what solutions have you adopted as a team?

On a scale from 1 to 5, how would you rate this activity?

5 out of 5

What have you learned from this activity?

I learned how to adapt a children's story into a play by using simple dialogues and expressive gestures.

How would you rate teamwork?

Excellent

What were the positive aspects of your teamwork?

We worked very well together in all the aspects of our performance.

What aspects of teamwork do you think need improving?

Nothing

Poetry

How did the activity go?

Very well

Have you encountered any difficulties?

No

If so, what solutions have you adopted as a team?

On a scale from 1 to 5, how would you rate this activity?

4 out of 5

What have you learned from this activity?

With this activity, I learned how to play with words, express my emotions, and structure poetry in a creative way.

How would you rate teamwork?

Excellent

What were the positive aspects of your teamwork?

Creativity and teamwork in general.

What aspects of teamwork do you think need improving?

Nothing

Presentation and radio

How did the activity go?

Very well

Have you encountered any difficulties?

No

If so, what solutions have you adopted as a team?

On a scale from 1 to 5, how would you rate this activity?

4 out of 5

What have you learned from this activity?

A lot about children's literature and its genres, working as a team, and expressing myself in French. I liked working with the radio even though our recording was a bit short.

How would you rate teamwork?

Good

What were the positive aspects of your teamwork?

Our disposition for work, our work management and our collaboration for the project.

What aspects of teamwork do you think need improving?

Being a bit more available.

Student 9

Oral literature

How did the activity go?

Very well

Have you encountered any difficulties?

No

If so, what solutions have you adopted as a team?

On a scale from 1 to 5, how would you rate this activity?

5 out of 5

What have you learned from this activity?

Yes, I learned about other cultures.

How would you rate teamwork?

Excellent

What were the positive aspects of your teamwork?

Good coordination.

Good communication.

Creativity.

What aspects of teamwork do you think need improving?

In my opinion, I didn't find any areas for improvement.

Comics

How did the activity go?

Very well

Have you encountered any difficulties?

No

If so, what solutions have you adopted as a team?

On a scale from 1 to 5, how would you rate this activity?

5 out of 5

What have you learned from this activity?

I've learned to use other technological resources for creating comics.

How would you rate teamwork?

Excellent

What were the positive aspects of your teamwork?

Good communication and creativity.

What aspects of teamwork do you think need improving?

In my opinion, we work well as a team.

Picturebooks

How did the activity go?

Very well

Have you encountered any difficulties?

No

If so, what solutions have you adopted as a team?

On a scale from 1 to 5, how would you rate this activity?

5 out of 5

What have you learned from this activity?

Yes, I learned to edit videos and create a script based on a children's picturebook.

How would you rate teamwork?

Excellent

What were the positive aspects of your teamwork?

Good communication and creativity.

What aspects of teamwork do you think need improving?

I don't think there's anything to improve.

Theater

How did the activity go?

Very well

Have you encountered any difficulties?

Yes

If so, what solutions have you adopted as a team?

Creating the materials.

On a scale from 1 to 5, how would you rate this activity?

5 out of 5

What have you learned from this activity?

I really like theater, and I have learned to communicate in French in a more effective way.

How would you rate teamwork?

Excellent

What were the positive aspects of your teamwork?

Organization, communication and creativity.

What aspects of teamwork do you think need improving?

Nothing.

Poetry

How did the activity go?

Very well

Have you encountered any difficulties?

No

If so, what solutions have you adopted as a team?

On a scale from 1 to 5, how would you rate this activity?

5 out of 5

What have you learned from this activity?

Poetry is a good tool to work with emotions.

How would you rate teamwork?

Excellent.

What were the positive aspects of your teamwork?

I am satisfied with my work and my team's.

What aspects of teamwork do you think need improving?

Nothing

Presentation and radio

How did the activity go?

Very well

Have you encountered any difficulties?

No

If so, what solutions have you adopted as a team?

On a scale from 1 to 5, how would you rate this activity?

5 out of 5

What have you learned from this activity?

Yes, I have learned about different genres and how to use them in the classroom

How would you rate teamwork?

Excellent

What were the positive aspects of your teamwork?

Good communication, good coordination and creativity.

What aspects of teamwork do you think need improving?

I think that we should improve our pronunciation.

Student 10

Oral literature

How did the activity go?

Very well

Have you encountered any difficulties?

No

If so, what solutions have you adopted as a team?

On a scale from 1 to 5, how would you rate this activity?

5 out of 5

What have you learned from this activity?

We learned songs from each region and the main elements of each, plus new languages related to French.

How would you rate teamwork?

Excellent

What were the positive aspects of your teamwork?

Each member worked on the parts they liked best, and we coordinated ourselves very well to complete the project, leaving enough time to resolve any unforeseen circumstances that arose.

What aspects of teamwork do you think need improving?

I mustn't stress about everything and take things more calmly.

Comics

How did the activity go?

Well

Have you encountered any difficulties?

Yes

If so, what solutions have you adopted as a team?

We were alert to any unforeseen circumstances that arose, and looked for other applications that appealed to us and offered more opportunities than the one proposed by the teacher.

On a scale from 1 to 5, how would you rate this activity?

4 out of 5

What have you learned from this activity?

I learned more vocabulary about animals and food in French, as well as how to create a comic strip on different platforms.

How would you rate teamwork?

Excellent

What were the positive aspects of your teamwork?

We organized ourselves well and, although we had a lot of work to do this week, we were able to adapt our time to do it.

What aspects of teamwork do you think need improving?

Patience and order, because I'm very messy.

Picturebooks

How did the activity go?

Very well

Have you encountered any difficulties?

Yes

If so, what solutions have you adopted as a team?

We encountered a few difficulties when making the videos, but we agreed to film and edit the videos all in the same way to make the final video look better.

On a scale from 1 to 5, how would you rate this activity?

5 out of 5

What have you learned from this activity?

I learned how to make a book trailer and edit videos.

How would you rate teamwork?

Excellent

What were the positive aspects of your teamwork?

Creativity

What aspects of teamwork do you think need improving?

I think we understand each other fairly well and I don't see anything to improve as far as the team is concerned.

Theater

How did the activity go?

Very well

Have you encountered any difficulties?

Yes

If so, what solutions have you adopted as a team?

I encountered difficulties when preparing the materials because we didn't have much time. However, we organized ourselves well so that we could complete them together.

On a scale from 1 to 5, how would you rate this activity?

5 out of 5

What have you learned from this activity?

I learned how to create a play by interacting with the audience.

How would you rate teamwork?

Excellent

What were the positive aspects of your teamwork?

Organization and mutual aid.

What aspects of teamwork do you think need improving?

Nothing.

Poetry

How did the activity go?

Very well

Have you encountered any difficulties?

Yes

If so, what solutions have you adopted as a team?

When it came time to create the calligram, we couldn't find a website to make it online, so we finally decided to do it on paper.

On a scale from 1 to 5, how would you rate this activity?

5 out of 5

What have you learned from this activity?

Poetry is a good resource for working on emotions with students, as well as being fun and entertaining.

How would you rate teamwork?

Excellent

What were the positive aspects of your teamwork?

We did a great job in all aspects

What aspects of teamwork do you think need improving?

Nothing

Presentation and radio

How did the activity go?

Very well

Have you encountered any difficulties?

No

If so, what solutions have you adopted as a team?

On a scale from 1 to 5, how would you rate this activity?

5 out of 5

What have you learned from this activity?

I learned more about poetry as well as the topics presented by my classmates in a more entertaining way than if it had been explained in class in a traditional way. However, when recording the radio program, I made several mistakes because I became nervous.

How would you rate teamwork?

Excellent

What were the positive aspects of your teamwork?

Creativity, timeliness and organization. I think we have all worked together effectively and we understood each other.

What aspects of teamwork do you think need improving?

Pronunciation and comprehension in French

Student 11

Oral literature

How did the activity go?

Very well

Have you encountered any difficulties?

No

If so, what solutions have you adopted as a team?

On a scale from 1 to 5, how would you rate this activity?

5 out of 5

What have you learned from this activity?

In this activity, we learned about the different regions of France and their traditions, as well as their flags, typical animals and songs, which we loved to perform and record on the radio.

How would you rate teamwork?

Excellent

What were the positive aspects of your teamwork?

We were all well-coordinated and learned a lot from each other. What's more, we were able to deal with any unforeseen circumstances that arose

What aspects of teamwork do you think need improving?

Not being stressed by anything and knowing how to stay calm in situations where I'm afraid I wouldn't know how to solve a work issue.

Comics

How did the activity go?

Well

Have you encountered any difficulties?

Yes

If so, what solutions have you adopted as a team?

We always relied on each other. In addition, we sought out various resources to guide us in the realization of our work.

On a scale from 1 to 5, how would you rate this activity?

4 out of 5

What have you learned from this activity?

I learned vocabulary about animals and food in French. Also, I learned how to make a comic book with the help of an app called Storyboardthat (although it was not free).

How would you rate teamwork?

Excellent

What were the positive aspects of your teamwork?

We organized ourselves well even though we had much work to do that week.

What aspects of teamwork do you think need improving?

Patience and better time management.

Picturebooks

How did the activity go?

Very well

Have you encountered any difficulties?

No

If so, what solutions have you adopted as a team?

The ideas we had were that each member of the team should record a scene and then we will bring them together to create our video. We also had to choose the phrases from the book that we considered the most important for the film.

On a scale from 1 to 5, how would you rate this activity?

5 out of 5

What have you learned from this activity?

I learned how to make movie trailers and edit videos by attaching lyrics.

How would you rate teamwork?

Excellent

What were the positive aspects of your teamwork?

Each of us brought our own knowledge and strengths to the table, allowing us to approach the tasks from different angles and enriching the final result. What's more, the division of tasks was more balanced, resulting in better time management and overall team efficiency.

What aspects of teamwork do you think need improving?

I think we complement each other very well, so there's nothing to improve.

Theater

How did the activity go?

Very well

Have you encountered any difficulties?

No

If so, what solutions have you adopted as a team?

On a scale from 1 to 5, how would you rate this activity?

5 out of 5

What have you learned from this activity?

I strengthened my skills in how to create and perform a play in a foreign language.

How would you rate teamwork?

Excellent

What were the positive aspects of your teamwork?

Among ourselves, we discussed how we were going to perform the play, prepared the materials, and finally rehearsed to ensure everything went smoothly.

What aspects of teamwork do you think need improving?

Nothing

Poetry

How did the activity go?

Very well

Have you encountered any difficulties?

No

If so, what solutions have you adopted as a team?

On a scale from 1 to 5, how would you rate this activity?

4 out of 5

What have you learned from this activity?

I learned more information about poetry and how to associate it with emotions.

How would you rate teamwork?

Excellent

What were the positive aspects of your teamwork?

We all had a positive attitude, and the solutions were agreed upon among us.

What aspects of teamwork do you think need improving?

Nothing

Presentation and radio

How did the activity go?

Very well

Have you encountered any difficulties?

No

If so, what solutions have you adopted as a team?

On a scale from 1 to 5, how would you rate this activity?

5 out of 5

What have you learned from this activity?

I learned how to work with poetry (our genre) when teaching children a foreign language and more about this and other subjects.

How would you rate teamwork?

Excellent

What were the positive aspects of your teamwork?

Working in a team allowed all members to contribute their ideas, which enriched the information. Moreover, communication between us was very good.

What aspects of teamwork do you think need improving?

Improve pronunciation in French.

Student 12

Oral literature

How did the activity go?

Very well

Have you encountered any difficulties?

No

If so, what solutions have you adopted as a team?

On a scale from 1 to 5, how would you rate this activity?

5 out of 5

What have you learned from this activity?

The best way to pronounce certain words that appeared on the songs. I found the activity interesting, especially the fact of singing and being able to listen to our pronunciation, it seems to me that it can avoid repeating mistakes.

How would you rate teamwork?

Good

What were the positive aspects of your teamwork?

All the work we do is always cooperative, helping each other out, resolving doubts and exchanging the information we find.

What aspects of teamwork do you think need improving?

Sometimes it's hard to agree on the best solution, but we always find a way.

Comics

How did the activity go?

Very well

Have you encountered any difficulties?

Yes

If so, what solutions have you adopted as a team?

We had trouble choosing the images in the applications.

On a scale from 1 to 5, how would you rate this activity?

5 out of 5

What have you learned from this activity?

How to teach children how to use apps to design comics and how to explain content in a dynamic, interactive way. It was a different activity that I'd never had the chance to try, and it seemed interesting to work on in the classroom, for our future as teachers.

How would you rate teamwork?

Excellent

What were the positive aspects of your teamwork?

All the work was discussed in advance and worked out in such a way that we all agreed. What's more, the activity was carried out jointly and simultaneously.

What aspects of teamwork do you think need improving?

A member of our team is too much of a perfectionist, and when the whole exercise was already done, they told us it didn't suit them, and we had to change it several times. That's why I think we should have communicated more about the option that best suited the project.

Picturebooks

How did the activity go?

Very well

Have you encountered any difficulties?

No

If so, what solutions have you adopted as a team?

On a scale from 1 to 5, how would you rate this activity?

5 out of 5

What have you learned from this activity?

I think it was a different but fun activity, which enabled us as students to learn more about the creation of booktrailers and to be able to create similar activities suited to our future as teachers.

How would you rate teamwork?

Excellent

What were the positive aspects of your teamwork?

As in every activity, I always emphasize teamwork, and the fact that all opinions and suggestions count. No one works more or less, we're all one.

What aspects of teamwork do you think need improving?

Availability, but that's a difficult subject to solve because everyone has their own obligations, jobs or limited schedules, as is my case. Maybe that's the hardest part of teamwork, planning schedules to do activities together.

Theater

How did the activity go?

Very well

Have you encountered any difficulties?

No

If so, what solutions have you adopted as a team?

On a scale from 1 to 5, how would you rate this activity?

5 out of 5

What have you learned from this activity?

I learned how to create a theatrical play based on a picturebook.

How would you rate teamwork?

Excellent

What were the positive aspects of your teamwork?

Teamwork, and the fact that all our opinions and suggestions count.

What aspects of teamwork do you think need improving?

Nothing

Poetry

How did the activity go?

Very well

Have you encountered any difficulties?

No

If so, what solutions have you adopted as a team?

On a scale from 1 to 5, how would you rate this activity?

5 out of 5

What have you learned from this activity?

It was a way of learning how to make calligrams, since I had never made one before. On the other hand, poetry has always been a weakness for me, so working with my team makes it a richer experience.

How would you rate teamwork?

Excellent

What were the positive aspects of your teamwork?

We helped each other during this activity.

What aspects of teamwork do you think need improving?

Nothing.

Presentation and radio

How did the activity go?

Very well

Have you encountered any difficulties?

No

If so, what solutions have you adopted as a team?

On a scale from 1 to 5, how would you rate this activity?

5 out of 5

What have you learned from this activity?

I discovered children's books of Francophone origin that I didn't know before, learned about the history of theater and its impact, and about famous French authors... I learned how to edit a podcast and include music.

How would you rate teamwork?

Excellent

What were the positive aspects of your teamwork?

Creativity and communication amongst the members of the team.

What aspects of teamwork do you think need improving?

Nothing

Student 13

Oral literature

How did the activity go?

Very well

Have you encountered any difficulties?

No

If so, what solutions have you adopted as a team?

On a scale from 1 to 5, how would you rate this activity?

5 out of 5

What have you learned from this activity?

I was able to discover French nursery rhymes and learn more about the different regions of France.

How would you rate teamwork?

Excellent

What were the positive aspects of your teamwork?

Our main positive aspect was that we all worked actively and showed great interest in the work, which enabled us to complete it quickly.

What aspects of teamwork do you think need improving?

Maybe one thing I could improve on is bringing more ideas and opinions to the team.

Comics

How did the activity go?

Very well

Have you encountered any difficulties?

No

If so, what solutions have you adopted as a team?

On a scale from 1 to 5, how would you rate this activity?

5 out of 5

What have you learned from this activity?

I learned how to work with tools to create comics, and how to create comics that teach content in French.

How would you rate teamwork?

Excellent

What were the positive aspects of your teamwork?

We all worked fairly and shared the tasks well.

What aspects of teamwork do you think need improving?

I don't think there are any aspects of this work that I need to improve. I think I've worked well and contributed with new ideas.

Picturebooks

How did the activity go?

Very well

Have you encountered any difficulties?

No

If so, what solutions have you adopted as a team?

On a scale from 1 to 5, how would you rate this activity?

5 out of 5

What have you learned from this activity?

Thanks to this work, I've been able to practice my French orally and, what's more, it's a way of working on storytelling with children.

How would you rate teamwork?

Excellent

What were the positive aspects of your teamwork?

We were well organized and we all worked hard.

What aspects of teamwork do you think need improving?

I think I need to improve my ability to always express my ideas and opinions.

Theater

How did the activity go?

Very well

Have you encountered any difficulties?

Yes

If so, what solutions have you adopted as a team?

Even though we encountered some difficulties, such as an unexpected issue and the lack of materials, thanks to dialogue and the role of the coordinator, we managed to find appropriate and feasible solutions on time.

On a scale from 1 to 5, how would you rate this activity?

5 out of 5

What have you learned from this activity?

During this activity, I mainly learned how to interpret a story through dramatization and body language. We also learned to use literature as both a leisure and learning tool. It is also worth mentioning that we learned to handle a major unexpected event, the absence of one of our members and the materials they were supposed to provide, by adapting and overcoming the difficulties.

How would you rate teamwork?

Excellent

What were the positive aspects of your teamwork?

I would highlight cooperation and dialogue, as it has helped us to solve an unexpected issue.

What aspects of teamwork do you think need improving?

Nothing

Poetry

How did the activity go?

Very well

Have you encountered any difficulties?

No

If so, what solutions have you adopted as a team?

On a scale from 1 to 5, how would you rate this activity?

5 out of 5

What have you learned from this activity?

I learned how to work with different types of poetry in French.

How would you rate teamwork?

Excellent

What were the positive aspects of your teamwork?

Everything

What aspects of teamwork do you think need improving?

Nothing

Presentation and radio

How did the activity go?

Very well

Have you encountered any difficulties?

No

If so, what solutions have you adopted as a team?

On a scale from 1 to 5, how would you rate this activity?

5 out of 5

What have you learned from this activity?

I learned a lot about oral tradition literature and also other genres through the work of my classmates.

How would you rate teamwork?

Excellent

What were the positive aspects of your teamwork?

The strengths of our teamwork were communication and organization.

What aspects of teamwork do you think need improving?

I don't think there are any aspects to improve since we have worked very well as a team.

Student 14

Oral literature

How did the activity go?

Very well

Have you encountered any difficulties?

Yes

If so, what solutions have you adopted as a team?

My main difficulty was still the pronunciation of certain parts of the song, and the team helped me correct it.

On a scale from 1 to 5, how would you rate this activity?

5 out of 5

What have you learned from this activity?

I discovered a region I didn't know, like Auvergne-Rhône-Alpes, and, above all, typical aspects of different regions of France. I also acquired vocabulary related to the culture and, once again, I understood the value of songs in learning a language. I found it an interesting activity where we not only worked as a team, but also collaborated at times with the rest of our classmates.

How would you rate teamwork?

Excellent

What were the positive aspects of your teamwork?

I think we have done an outstanding job of fulfilling the responsibilities and roles assumed in the initial commitment. I also emphasize the dedication and cooperative work, both in and out of the classroom.

What aspects of teamwork do you think need improving?

Perhaps, from a general point of view, the aesthetic aspect of the productions and materials resulting from the teamwork, as well as the effort to speak more French among us when possible.

Comics

How did the activity go?

Well

Have you encountered any difficulties?

Yes

If so, what solutions have you adopted as a team?

The main difficulty in this case was coordination and time management. The solution was therefore to agree on a compensatory division of roles during the presentation day, allocating more time to the person who has been able to devote less time to it in class, for justified reasons of course.

On a scale from 1 to 5, how would you rate this activity?

4 out of 5

What have you learned from this activity?

I learned how to use two new digital applications to create comic strips, while at the same time gaining the knowledge that comics, a very attractive format for children, can be a good way of teaching or learning aspects related to a foreign language, in this case French. I think it was a very interesting and relaxed activity that help us to discover other methods of teaching a language while perfecting our vocabulary and improving our pronunciation when reading.

How would you rate teamwork?

Good

What were the positive aspects of your teamwork?

Recognize individual effort and balance responsibilities between tasks.

What aspects of teamwork do you think need improving?

I think it would be a good idea to improve coordination.

Picturebooks

How did the activity go?

Very well

Have you encountered any difficulties?

Yes

If so, what solutions have you adopted as a team?

At first, we had our doubts about the exact structure the booktrailer should have, but then, following the established criteria, we decided to give free rein to our imagination and creativity, in order to create something that could be both fun and attractive to the viewer, beyond simply telling a story.

On a scale from 1 to 5, how would you rate this activity?

5 out of 5

What have you learned from this activity?

In addition to discovering that some of the children's stories I read as a child were written by French authors, I learned how to use ICT for pedagogical and literary purposes, discovering that these, along with audiovisual resources, can become the best way of bringing students closer to reading, given the digitized society we live in. It was fun and a bit stressful at the same time, which, despite the distance, made it possible to work as a team and create a creative product that would meet

expectations, despite a few obstacles like time management (due to personal and particular problems) ... But in general, I'd do it all over again.

How would you rate teamwork?

Excellent

What were the positive aspects of your teamwork?

The positive points were the unanimous agreements reached regarding the chosen tale, the script and responsibilities, as well as the coordination and contribution during the production of our booktrailer, choosing the spaces to be filmed, the scenes, the objects...

What aspects of teamwork do you think need improving?

Personally, I can't stand the pressures of rushing, and I think one of the things we need to improve is time management.

Theater

How did the activity go?

Very well

Have you encountered any difficulties?

Yes

If so, what solutions have you adopted as a team?

Even though we encountered some difficulties, such as an unexpected issue and the lack of materials we ultimately didn't have, thanks to dialogue and the role of the coordinator, we managed to find appropriate and feasible solutions on time.

On a scale from 1 to 5, how would you rate this activity?

5 out of 5

What have you learned from this activity?

During this activity, I mainly learned how to interpret a story through dramatization and body language. We also learned to use literature as both a leisure and learning tool. It is also worth mentioning that we learned to handle a major unexpected event, the absence of one of our members and the materials they were supposed to provide, by adapting and overcoming the difficulties.

How would you rate teamwork?

Excellent

What were the positive aspects of your teamwork?

I would highlight cooperation and dialogue, as it has helped us to solve an unexpected issue.

What aspects of teamwork do you think need improving?

Nothing

Poetry

How did the activity go?

Very well

Have you encountered any difficulties?

Yes

If so, what solutions have you adopted as a team?

The main difficulty was dividing the work so that one of our teammates could also work from home while they were sick. The solution was to assign tasks that wouldn't prevent us from continuing to make progress. Additionally, creating the calligram seemed somewhat complicated. However, after reading the teachers' slideshow and watching a tutorial on YouTube, we managed to complete it.

On a scale from 1 to 5, how would you rate this activity?

5 out of 5

What have you learned from this activity?

Primarily, I think I learned a way to work on emotional intelligence and emotions from a very young age, an aspect often difficult because children can show some resistance to opening up. This activity also allowed me to enrich my French vocabulary by discovering new words related to emotions and feelings, as well as rhymes to use them in a poetic and creative context.

How would you rate teamwork?

Excellent

What were the positive aspects of your teamwork?

We were able to solve the issue by talking to each other and reaching an agreement.

What aspects of teamwork do you think need improving?

Nothing

Presentation and radio

How did the activity go?

Well

Have you encountered any difficulties?

Yes

If so, what solutions have you adopted as a team?

My main difficulty is pronunciation. That's why the solution agreed upon by the team was for each member to choose the part of the work they wanted to present. This allowed us to feel more comfortable speaking in public in French. Additionally, another aspect to highlight was the distribution of time. Despite our efforts to share it fairly, the members most comfortable with the language took a bit more time during the presentation.

On a scale from 1 to 5, how would you rate this activity?

5 out of 5

What have you learned from this activity?

I mainly acquired strategies and activities that are, in my opinion, very useful and beneficial when it comes to learning a foreign language, helping to gain fluency and improve aspects such as pronunciation.

How would you rate teamwork?

Excellent

What were the positive aspects of your teamwork?

The interest in carrying out the activity, meeting up and dedicating time at home for its preparation, asking for feedback from the other members. It's also worth highlighting the respect for each person's different pace and linguistic circumstances. Working with my teammates was a real opportunity, but creating the podcast was especially fun. We complemented each other very well in writing the script, making sure everyone took part in every section and that there was interaction among the four of us. During the recording, I think we all gave our best, even if we may have lacked a bit more fluency and intonation at times. Other than that, I believe our expectations were fairly low, and the result of the podcast far exceeded them.

What aspects of teamwork do you think need improving?

Fluency and intonation, as well as individual responsibility, for example, by setting a specific deadline to complete the tasks, and not leaving the possibility open for someone to do it time minute and in a rush.

Student 16

Oral literature

How did the activity go?

Very well

Have you encountered any difficulties?

No

If so, what solutions have you adopted as a team?

On a scale from 1 to 5, how would you rate this activity?

5 out of 5

What have you learned from this activity?

More about French culture

How would you rate teamwork?

Excellent

What were the positive aspects of your teamwork?

Communication.

Work well done.

Organization.

What aspects of teamwork do you think need improving?

Nothing

Comics

How did the activity go?

Very well

Have you encountered any difficulties?

No

If so, what solutions have you adopted as a team?

On a scale from 1 to 5, how would you rate this activity?

5 out of 5

What have you learned from this activity?

How to create comics using an application for computers.

How would you rate teamwork?

Excellent

What were the positive aspects of your teamwork?

I believe we completed the assignment very fast because we are becoming used to the team dynamic.

What aspects of teamwork do you think need improving?

Nothing

Picturebooks

How did the activity go?

Very well

Have you encountered any difficulties?

Yes

If so, what solutions have you adopted as a team?

I had trouble speaking in French.

On a scale from 1 to 5, how would you rate this activity?

5 out of 5

What have you learned from this activity?

I learned how to record and edit a video focused on a children's story.

How would you rate teamwork?

Excellent

What were the positive aspects of your teamwork?

Communication and organization.

What aspects of teamwork do you think need improving?

Nothing

Theater

How did the activity go?

Very well

Have you encountered any difficulties?

Yes

If so, what solutions have you adopted as a team?

We had a few difficulties throughout the project, such as choosing the materials we will use for the performance and writing dialogues that will be easy to understand. The solutions were found were to talk everything through clearly and to work on the script together.

On a scale from 1 to 5, how would you rate this activity?

5 out of 5

What have you learned from this activity?

I have learned a lot about developing my French language skills and overcoming my stage fright. I feel more comfortable with speaking the language now, and I'm no longer shy.

How would you rate teamwork?

Excellent

What were the positive aspects of your teamwork?

We worked very well together and we overcame our difficulties

What aspects of teamwork do you think need improving?

Nothing

Poetry

How did the activity go?

Very well

Have you encountered any difficulties?

No

If so, what solutions have you adopted as a team?

On a scale from 1 to 5, how would you rate this activity?

5 out of 5

What have you learned from this activity?

In this activity, I learned to express myself better. I discovered that poetry is a very good resource to introduce in the French classroom when teaching a foreign language.

How would you rate teamwork?

Excellent

What were the positive aspects of your teamwork?

All aspects of teamwork were good.

What aspects of teamwork do you think need improving?

We didn't find any difficulty.

Presentation and radio

How did the activity go?

Very well

Have you encountered any difficulties?

No

If so, what solutions have you adopted as a team?

On a scale from 1 to 5, how would you rate this activity?

5 out of 5

What have you learned from this activity?

I learned a lot of information thanks to the presentations and recordings of my classmates.

How would you rate teamwork?

Excellent

What were the positive aspects of your teamwork?

We have worked communicatively and without any problems. I love doing projects with my classmates

What aspects of teamwork do you think need improving?

Spend more time doing the activity.

Student 17

Oral literature

How did the activity go?

Very well

Have you encountered any difficulties?

No

If so, what solutions have you adopted as a team?

On a scale from 1 to 5, how would you rate this activity?

5 out of 5

What have you learned from this activity?

I improved my French and learned new information about Corsica and the Île-de-France.

How would you rate teamwork?

Excellent

What were the positive aspects of your teamwork?

Willingness to work and originality.

What aspects of teamwork do you think need improving?

We should improve our organization and distribution of tasks between the members

Comics

How did the activity go?

Very well

Have you encountered any difficulties?

No

If so, what solutions have you adopted as a team?

On a scale from 1 to 5, how would you rate this activity?

5 out of 5

What have you learned from this activity?

I learned how to use programs to create comic strips and how to use them in a fun way to learn new vocabulary and expressions.

How would you rate teamwork?

Excellent

What were the positive aspects of your teamwork?

Our organization.

What aspects of teamwork do you think need improving?

Nothing.

Picturebooks

How did the activity go?

Very well

Have you encountered any difficulties?

No

If so, what solutions have you adopted as a team?

On a scale from 1 to 5, how would you rate this activity?

5 out of 5

What have you learned from this activity?

I learned how to rewrite a story in a video format, and what's more, I practiced my pronunciation and learned new vocabulary.

How would you rate teamwork?

Excellent

What were the positive aspects of your teamwork?

The organization of tasks and the will to complete them despite being on holidays (Easter).

What aspects of teamwork do you think need improving?

I believe that, although our communication has significantly improved, there is still room for improvement.

Theater

How did the activity go?

Very well

Have you encountered any difficulties?

No

If so, what solutions have you adopted as a team?

On a scale from 1 to 5, how would you rate this activity?

5 out of 5

What have you learned from this activity?

I learned how to create a theatrical performance based on a children's picturebook, acquired new vocabulary and practiced my pronunciation.

How would you rate teamwork?

Excellent

What were the positive aspects of your teamwork?

Cooperation and mutual aid.

What aspects of teamwork do you think need improving?

Nothing

Poetry

How did the activity go?

Very well

Have you encountered any difficulties?

No

If so, what solutions have you adopted as a team?

On a scale from 1 to 5, how would you rate this activity?

5 out of 5

What have you learned from this activity?

I learned new vocabulary in French, how to create a calligram online, and what a tautogram is.

How would you rate teamwork?

Excellent

What were the positive aspects of your teamwork?

Cooperation and creativity.

What aspects of teamwork do you think need improving?

Nothing

Presentation and radio

How did the activity go?

Very well

Have you encountered any difficulties?

No

If so, what solutions have you adopted as a team?

On a scale from 1 to 5, how would you rate this activity?

5 out of 5

What have you learned from this activity?

With this activity, I improved my French, expanded my knowledge of comic books and other genres, and learned how to teach them in a primary school classroom using the radio as a resource.

How would you rate teamwork?

Excellent

What were the positive aspects of your teamwork?

Participation and availability.

What aspects of teamwork do you think need improving?

Communication within the team.

Student 18

Oral literature

How did the activity go?

Very well

Have you encountered any difficulties?

No

If so, what solutions have you adopted as a team?

On a scale from 1 to 5, how would you rate this activity?

4 out of 5

What have you learned from this activity?

I think it's a very complete activity that could be perfectly adapted to a classroom with the aim of bringing children closer to the culture and traditions of the different regions of France. In fact, I found it a super-creative activity to do in small teams, although it's true that the only drawback I'd put to this activity would be not having done all the regions (as the map looked a bit strange with the empty regions).

How would you rate teamwork?

Excellent

What were the positive aspects of your teamwork?

I believe that communication and the sharing of creative ideas were our strengths.

What aspects of teamwork do you think need improving?

I think we need to improve the speed of execution.

Comics

How did the activity go?

Very well

Have you encountered any difficulties?

Yes

If so, what solutions have you adopted as a team?

It was difficult to work with the recommended applications because, when it came to creating the illustrations, there weren't enough graphic resources related to the theme of the comic strip: the farm and its animals.

On a scale from 1 to 5, how would you rate this activity?

5 out of 5

What have you learned from this activity?

I learned to use new resources, even if I then had to redirect the idea by using an application I'd already worked with: Canva. I really enjoyed creating these stories and being able to experience the whole creative process (before and after).

How would you rate teamwork?

Excellent

What were the positive aspects of your teamwork?

Creativity and team coordination.

What aspects of teamwork do you think need improving?

We need to improve the time, optimize it a little more.

Picturebooks

How did the activity go?

Very well

Have you encountered any difficulties?

Yes

If so, what solutions have you adopted as a team?

We had some problems when it came to approaching certain shots of the video because, having some ideas in mind, we had to adapt to the circumstances and the tools we had.

On a scale from 1 to 5, how would you rate this activity?

5 out of 5

What have you learned from this activity?

I really liked how I was able to approach one of the classics that almost everyone knows in real life and as a "trailer" so to speak. I also learned new things about shots and editing during the filming.

How would you rate teamwork?

Excellent

What were the positive aspects of your teamwork?

The creativity and ease with which the ideas came up. I also believe that we are always there when a problem arises and we try to find a solution.

What aspects of teamwork do you think need improving?

I think we could improve some things regarding the video itself, such as technical or editing issues.

Theater

How did the activity go?

Very well

Have you encountered any difficulties?

Yes

If so, what solutions have you adopted as a team?

We had trouble figuring out how to include everything we wanted: sound, dialogues, pauses, gestures... The solution we adopted was to coordinate our staging so that we could see what each of us could do. It was also essential to meet up occasionally to rehearse together.

On a scale from 1 to 5, how would you rate this activity?

5 out of 5

What have you learned from this activity?

In my case, I had already done a similar activity last term as part of my Spanish course, and just like this time, it was a bit challenging at first, but I ended up really enjoying both designing it and putting it into practice.

How would you rate teamwork?

Excellent

What were the positive aspects of your teamwork?

I think we can highlight our coordination and good management of time.

What aspects of teamwork do you think need improving?

Nothing

Poetry

How did the activity go?

Very well

Have you encountered any difficulties?

Yes

If so, what solutions have you adopted as a team?

When it came to creating the calligram, we had to end up doing it by hand because we couldn't find any app to help us make it the way we wanted.

On a scale from 1 to 5, how would you rate this activity?

4 out of 5

What have you learned from this activity?

Thanks to this activity, I learned that emotions are a great way of working with poetry. After all, what is the purpose of these compositions, if not to express feelings and opinions?

How would you rate teamwork?

Excellent

What were the positive aspects of your teamwork?

Every aspect of teamwork

What aspects of teamwork do you think need improving?

Nothing

Presentation and radio

How did the activity go?

Very well

Have you encountered any difficulties?

No

If so, what solutions have you adopted as a team?

On a scale from 1 to 5, how would you rate this activity?

5 out of 5

What have you learned from this activity?

In addition to discovering how the different literary genres for children and adolescents, this activity can help us, preservice teachers, to get closer to a language and better understand it, just as children do, I learned new vocabulary and aspects of pronunciation that I didn't know before. I would also like to say that another aspect I learned was related to the practice itself, particularly regarding body language and connecting with the audience through eye contact, which is a very important aspect, as well as the use of voice during recordings.

How would you rate teamwork?

Excellent

What were the positive aspects of your teamwork?

I would like to highlight interest and engagement in the preparation of the project, saving time to personally meet to prepare. We have also exchanged opinions and impressions in a constructive and positive way.

What aspects of teamwork do you think need improving?

Nothing

Student 19

Oral literature

How did the activity go?

Very well

Have you encountered any difficulties?

No

If so, what solutions have you adopted as a team?

On a scale from 1 to 5, how would you rate this activity?

5 out of 5

What have you learned from this activity?

This activity has allowed me to discover the potential of songs and the different regions in France

How would you rate teamwork?

Good

What were the positive aspects of your teamwork?

Good ambiance and cooperation.

What aspects of teamwork do you think need improving?

A better distribution of workload.

Comics

How did the activity go?

Very well

Have you encountered any difficulties?

No

If so, what solutions have you adopted as a team?

On a scale from 1 to 5, how would you rate this activity?

5 out of 5

What have you learned from this activity?

I learned how to use a platform that will enable me to create comics in a simple way. What's more, I've learned that comics are a very attractive and effective way of teaching a language, both to children and adults.

How would you rate teamwork?

Excellent

What were the positive aspects of your teamwork?

Teamwork in general and communication.

What aspects of teamwork do you think need improving?

Nothing

Picturebooks

How did the activity go?

Very well

Have you encountered any difficulties?

No

If so, what solutions have you adopted as a team?

On a scale from 1 to 5, how would you rate this activity?

4 out of 5

What have you learned from this activity?

Tell a story more creatively using new technologies.

How would you rate teamwork?

Good

What were the positive aspects of your teamwork?

There was no major disagreement on how to carry out the work.

What aspects of teamwork do you think need improving?

A better distribution of the workload.

Theater

How did the activity go?

Well

Have you encountered any difficulties?

No

If so, what solutions have you adopted as a team?

On a scale from 1 to 5, how would you rate this activity?

5 out of 5

What have you learned from this activity?

Thanks to this activity, I learned that it is possible for a book that originally doesn't involve audience participation, to include spectators. This is very useful in primary school, as it involves the students and gives them an active role.

How would you rate teamwork?

Excellent

What were the positive aspects of your teamwork?

We worked very well together.

What aspects of teamwork do you think need improving?

Nothing

Poetry

How did the activity go?

Very well

Have you encountered any difficulties?

No

If so, what solutions have you adopted as a team?

On a scale from 1 to 5, how would you rate this activity?

5 out of 5

What have you learned from this activity?

Make a more poetic use of the French language.

How would you rate teamwork?

Excellent

What were the positive aspects of your teamwork?

We complemented each other very well as a team.

What aspects of teamwork do you think need improving?

Nothing

Presentation and radio

How did the activity go?

Very well

Have you encountered any difficulties?

No

If so, what solutions have you adopted as a team?

On a scale from 1 to 5, how would you rate this activity?

5 out of 5

What have you learned from this activity?

I learned a bit more about our teams' genre: comic books. Additionally, this project allowed me to discover the potential of comics and the use of the radio in the classroom. It also made me think about how comics can be used in class and the activities we can do with them.

How would you rate teamwork?

Good

What were the positive aspects of your teamwork?

The work's environment was good.

What aspects of teamwork do you think need improving?

Better distribution of the workload.

Final questionnaire

What are your opinions on the course and the methodology used? Do you think you will implement this methodology in your future teaching practice?

- I really liked the project that we did on the subject. I think that throughout the Primary Education degree there are very few subjects (almost none unfortunately) that focused on future teaching practice and that serve to train us as “real teachers”. However, this course has surprised me a lot and I think I finished the course with a big bag of resources, methodology, different “projects” ... that I am sure that they will be very useful for my future as a teacher and that I will certainly put them into practice. In spite of my low level of French, I consider that I have learned a lot. This learning and improvement are thanks to this type of project, as it is very enriching and motivating for us. I encourage you to continue with this type of project in future courses that you really teach.
- I really liked the project and the activities we did because now we have more knowledge to apply them in the classroom.
- I really liked the course; it was very interesting and interactive and useful for our learning as future teachers.
- Overall, this project taught me many things that helped improve both my knowledge and my skills in French, as well as pedagogical knowledge on how to implement PBL in a primary school classroom.
- It was a very dynamic and interesting course, full of very interesting activities and resources to put into practice and if possible, to learn too.
- I really enjoyed doing this project because, in my case, I found it to be very creative and fun and very useful for our future practice as teachers.
- I consider that the course is well structured, and the classes are very dynamic, which helps a lot in understanding the subject's content.
- Congratulations on the development of the course. I believe I learned a lot in a more dynamic way that we can implement in the future. Also, the activities (like the poetry one) broke away from the stereotypes usually associated with certain types of reading, which helped maintain interest.
- The subject Foreign Language through Children's Literature is a subject that I really liked because I think that the teacher worked with us as I would like to work with children, in a very practical way, learning by ourselves and not in a theoretical way. We had to do a lot of activities about what we were teaching and that way we learned how to do it, we learned the content. I liked it a lot.
- Foreign Language through Children's Literature was for me a very nice subject. The teacher showed us many books. Besides, I liked the way of teaching, I liked the subject a lot because it was like working by projects. I feel like I learned a lot and besides, the teacher offers a lot of resources. I liked this one very much.
- This year in Foreign Language through Children's Literature, we worked on the different types of literature in a playful way, and it really encouraged creativity. And, for example, with the songs we had to research them and sing one on the radio. Then with the comic we had to create a comic, we also created a book trailer, we had to do a theatrical performance, and we recorded a radio program. I think it's a very playful way of learning a language and at the end it doesn't seem like you're in class learning verbs, learning vocabulary, because you learn it by playing.

- I really liked the subject because the teacher taught us how to teach children. That is to say, we worked with poetry and things like that, but specifically for Primary and Childhood Education children. At the end of the day this is what our degree should prepare us for.
- This subject was quite active and participative. There was a lot of cooperative work, practically everything was cooperative. And I do consider that I learned because, for example, I started the course without knowing much French and learned a lot, especially vocabulary, structures... by practicing through games, activities and things like that, not only by completing exercises. In this subject, we worked cooperatively, among ourselves and mostly sharing with other classmates, through expositions, games and activities, and I really liked it.